

Adaption of Fuel-Cell Energy in Aviation Infrastructure

Omar ALHARASEES^{1*}, Utku KALE¹

¹ Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Faculty of Transportation Engineering and Vehicle Engineering, Department of Aeronautics and Naval Architecture, Address: Budapest, 1111, Hungary

* E-mail: oyalharasees@edu.bme.hu

Abstract

This study meticulously analyzes the integration of fuel cell technology in aviation infrastructures and airports, employing the robust Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology. The investigation encompasses vital criteria such as environmental impact, technological feasibility, economic viability, and reliability, considering factors like carbon emissions reduction potential, air and noise pollution mitigation, resource sustainability, existing infrastructure compatibility, technological maturity, energy efficiency, initial investment costs, operational and maintenance expenses, long-term cost savings, system reliability, energy source stability, and grid connectivity. By applying the AHP model, this comprehensive assessment provides nuanced insights for aviation stakeholders, facilitating informed decisions toward sustainable energy choices.

Keywords: Fuel Cell Technology, Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), Aviation Sustainability, Environmental Impact, Energy Source Integration.

I. Introduction

In an era marked by intersecting environmental, technological, economic, and reliability considerations, the aviation industry confronts an imperative to reassess its energy sources (Jia, Macário and Buyle, 2023). A pivotal player in global transportation, commerce, and connectivity (Kelemen, 2009), the aviation sector, comprising aircraft, airports, and airfields, simultaneously contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and environmental pollution (Hasan *et al.*, 2021). Tackling these challenges necessitates profoundly exploring diverse energy types and their seamless integration into aviation and airport infrastructures.

The aviation industry's carbon footprint stands as a critical concern, with sustainable energy solutions promising to mitigate its environmental impact (Zhang, Gudmundsson and Oum, 2010). This study delves into how distinct Factors can effectively reduce carbon emissions, mitigate air and noise pollution, and foster resource sustainability within aviation. Real-world instances, such as adopting electric ground support vehicles at airports and using sustainable aviation fuels in commercial flights, underscore the industry's dedication to sustainable practices.

Integrating new energy sources into aviation necessitates technological feasibility and compatibility with existing infrastructure. Governed by stringent regulations and characterized by intricate operational dynamics, the aviation industry demands energy solutions that seamlessly align with its complex ecosystem (Rojas-Michaga *et al.*, 2023). Technological advancements, exemplified by integrating solar panels into airport structures for electricity generation and the ongoing development of battery-electric aircraft, showcase efforts to make aviation more sustainable (Yıldız *et al.*, 2023).

The economic dimension is pivotal, and sustainability should not compromise profitability. This analysis will scrutinize the financial aspects of adopting various energy types, considering initial investment costs, operational and maintenance expenditures, and the potential for long-term cost savings. Initiatives like deploying electric ground vehicles at airports and investing in hydrogen infrastructure projects illuminate the economic dynamics within aviation's sustainable energy landscape.

Uninterrupted and dependable energy supply is paramount for aviation operations, where disruptions can have severe consequences. This article evaluates the reliability and resilience of different energy sources, encompassing system reliability, energy source stability, and grid connectivity options. The presence of cogeneration systems supplying electricity and heat to airport facilities underscores the importance of resilient energy solutions.

The aviation industry is constantly evolving, with increasing air travel demand and evolving operational needs. Energy solutions must be scalable to accommodate this growth and flexible to adapt to changing circumstances. We will investigate the critical factors in investing in the suitable energy type adaptability while considering its capacity to integrate with other energy sources. Solutions like grid-connected systems with energy storage capabilities exemplify adaptations to the dynamic aviation landscape (Rupcic *et al.*, 2023).

In this article, we explore diverse factors that affect fuel cell technology within the aviation and airport infrastructure context, subsequently conducting an Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) analysis (Alharasees and Kale, 2023). This analysis provides a panoramic understanding of the relevance and applicability of fuel cell technology in the aviation industry and airport infrastructures.

II. Methodology

In undertaking a meticulous evaluation of diverse fuel cell technology energy types for integration into aviation infrastructures and airports, this study adopts the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology. Recognized for its capacity to handle complex decision-making scenarios, AHP systematically structures the hierarchy of criteria and facilitates a comprehensive analysis (Saaty, 1980).

The foundation of our evaluation lies in the insights of 18 Aviation Experts, strategically categorized into two groups—aviation operators and managers. This grouping ensures a holistic perspective, incorporating the aviation industry's operational and managerial facets. These experts, possessing profound knowledge and experience,

played a pivotal role in providing nuanced judgments on the criteria under consideration.

The Saaty scale was employed to capture the qualitative judgments of the expert panel. This scale, a proven tool in decision-making processes, assigns numerical values to verbal judgments, allowing for a nuanced yet quantifiable representation of expert opinions. Table 1 delineates the Saaty scale as a reference guide for the experts in expressing their preferences and comparisons.

Table 1 Saaty Scale (Saaty, 2008)

Intensity of Importance	1	3	5	7	9	2, 4, 6, 8
Definition	Equal Importance	Moderate Importance	Strong Importance	Very Strong Importance	Extremely Strong Importance	Intermediate Values

Figure 1 presents the Aviation Infrastructure Fuel-Cell Hierarchical Model, representing the structured hierarchy of criteria. This visual aid showcases the interconnections and dependencies among the various criteria, providing a holistic view of the analytical framework.

Figure 1 Fuel-Cell Hierarchical Model.

Within this model, the hierarchical arrangement encapsulates four key strata, each probing a distinct facet of the integration of fuel cell technology energy types:

- **Environmental Impact Assessment:** The first stratum of the evaluation centers on the environmental impact of different energy types. Within this context, the current researcher meticulously scrutinizes the potential for reduction of carbon emissions, air and noise pollution, and the overarching theme of resource sustainability. Real-world implementations, such as the adoption of electric ground support vehicles at airports and the integration of sustainable aviation fuels in commercial flights, serve as benchmarks to elucidate the palpable impact on the industry's environmental stewardship.
- **Technological Feasibility Examination:** The second tier delves into the technological feasibility of incorporating diverse energy types into the aviation ecosystem. We assess their compatibility with existing infrastructure, gauging technological maturity and energy efficiency. Illustrations abound, including the integration of solar panels into airport structures for electricity generation and the ongoing development of battery-electric aircraft, signaling a pivotal leap in technological advancements tailored to render aviation more sustainable.
- **Economic Viability Analysis:** Financial considerations form the bedrock of our third tier of analysis. Economic viability encompasses a discerning examination of initial investment costs, operational and maintenance expenditures, and the prospect of long-term cost savings. Instances such as deploying electric ground vehicles at airports and investing in hydrogen infrastructure projects illuminate the economic dynamics underpinning aviation's sustainable energy landscape.
- **Reliability and Resilience Assessment:** The fourth stratum evaluates the reliability and resilience embedded within different energy sources. This encompasses an in-depth system reliability analysis, energy source stability, and grid connectivity options. Noteworthy deployments of cogeneration systems, adept at supplying electricity and heat to airport facilities, underscore the strategic imperative of resilient energy solutions within aviation operations.

The holistic evaluation conducted through the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology, considering the insights of 18 Aviation Experts, provides a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted dimensions surrounding integrating diverse fuel cell technology energy types in aviation and airport infrastructures. By

navigating through the environmental, technological, and economic aspects, this analysis illuminates a pathway for informed decision-making in pursuing sustainable energy solutions within the aviation industry.

III. Results & Discussions

The evaluation of fuel cell technology energy types within the context of aviation and airport infrastructures was conducted through the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) in this research. In this section, we present the weighted criteria evaluations by aviation managers and operators, shedding light on their distinctive perspectives. The Saaty scale served as the foundation for pairwise comparisons, ensuring a systematic and reliable assessment. As depicted in Table 2, aviation managers prioritize reliability and resilience (33.20%) as the top concern, emphasizing the need for a dependable energy supply. Environmental impact follows closely at 29.71%, showcasing a commitment to sustainability. Economic viability holds the third spot (27.44%), highlighting financial considerations. Technological feasibility receives the lowest weight (9.65%), indicating relatively lower importance in their considerations. This nuanced hierarchy provides critical insights into their decision-making dynamics.

Table 2 PCM of Aviation Managers

Aviation Managers					
Criteria	Environmental Impact	Technological Feasibility	Economic Viability	Reliability and Resilience	Weights
Environmental Impact	1.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	29.71%
Technological Feasibility	0.50	1.00	2.00	2.00	9.65%
Economic Viability	0.33	0.50	1.00	2.00	27.44%
Reliability and Resilience	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.00	33.20%
CR=0.05263	Sum=				100%

Turning to Table 3, which outlines the weighted criteria evaluation by aviation operators, a divergent perspective emerges. Environmental impact holds the highest weight at 39.27%, signifying a heightened focus on minimizing the environmental footprint within this expert group. Technological feasibility, economic viability, reliability, and resilience are assigned weights of 18.30%, 13.81%, and 28.62%, respectively. This distribution underscores aviation operators' distinctive emphasis on environmental considerations, echoing the broader industry trend.

Table 3 PCM of Aviation Operators.

Aviation Operators					
Criteria	Environmental Impact	Technological Feasibility	Economic Viability	Reliability and Resilience	Weights
Environmental Impact	1.00	4.00	4.00	1.00	39.27%
Technological Feasibility	0.25	1.00	2.00	0.50	18.30%
Economic Viability	0.25	0.50	1.00	0.50	13.81%
Reliability and Resilience	1.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	28.62%
CR=0.0745	Sum=				100%

Comparing these expert perspectives, it becomes evident that while both groups prioritize environmental impact, aviation managers allocate relatively higher importance to reliability and resilience, constituting 33.20% of their considerations. In contrast, while still valuing reliability and resilience, aviation operators place a more substantial emphasis on environmental impact, accounting for 39.27% of their weighted criteria. These nuanced differences highlight the varied perspectives and priorities within the aviation industry concerning sustainable energy adoption. Figure 2 further illustrates the comparative analysis between aviation managers and aviation operators. The radar graph visually reinforces the distinct weightings assigned by each group to environmental impact, technological feasibility, economic viability, reliability, and resilience. This graphical representation offers a succinct overview of the varying emphases and provides a foundation for more in-depth discussions on the implications of these distinct perspectives.

The weighted criteria evaluations underscore the multifaceted considerations concerning sustainable energy solutions within the aviation industry. The differing emphases of aviation managers and operators illuminate the complex decision-making landscape, providing valuable insights for stakeholders navigating the path toward a more sustainable aviation future.

Figure 2 AHP Main Criteria Comparison.

IV. Conclusion

This comprehensive study delves into the intricate landscape of integrating fuel cell technology into aviation infrastructures and airports, employing the robust Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology. The exploration considers critical criteria such as environmental impact, technological feasibility, economic viability, and reliability, providing nuanced insights for aviation stakeholders. The industry's commitment to sustainability is evident, particularly emphasizing reducing environmental impact and adopting diverse energy types.

Aviation managers prioritize reliability and resilience, emphasizing the need for a dependable energy supply, while environmental impact closely follows, showcasing a commitment to sustainability. Economic viability holds the third spot, and technological feasibility is less critical. In contrast, aviation operators prioritize environmental impact, highlighting their focus on minimizing the industry's ecological footprint.

These findings illuminate the complex decision-making dynamics within the aviation industry, providing valuable insights for stakeholders navigating toward a sustainable aviation future. As the industry grapples with evolving demands, the study informs strategic choices, fostering a more sustainable and resilient aviation landscape for the future.

References

- Alharasees, O. and Kale, U. (2023) 'Applying AHP for supplier selection in aviation: a multi-criteria decision-making approach', *International Journal of Sustainable Aviation*, 9(4), pp. 293–313. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSA.2023.134344>.
- Hasan, M.A. et al. (2021) 'Climate Change Mitigation Pathways for the Aviation Sector', *Sustainability 2021*, Vol. 13, Page 3656, 13(7), p. 3656. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU13073656>.
- Jia, X., Macário, R. and Buyle, S. (2023) 'Expanding Horizons: A Review of Sustainability Evaluation Methodologies in the Airport Sector and Beyond', *Sustainability 2023*, Vol. 15, Page 11584, 15(15), p. 11584. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU151511584>.
- Kelemen, Z. (2009) 'Airport information system integration by using message broker', *Periodica Polytechnica Transportation Engineering*, 37(1–2), pp. 15–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3311/PP.TR.2009-1-2.03>.
- Rojas-Michaga, M.F. et al. (2023) 'Sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) production through power-to-liquid (PtL): A combined techno-economic and life cycle assessment', *Energy Conversion and Management*, 292, p. 117427. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2023.117427>.
- Rupcic, L. et al. (2023) 'Environmental impacts in the civil aviation sector: Current state and guidance', *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 119, p. 103717. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRD.2023.103717>.
- Saaty, T.L. (2008) 'Decision making with the analytic hierarchy process', *International journal of services sciences*, 1(1), pp. 83–98. Available at: <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJSSci.2008.01759> (Accessed: 15 February 2022).
- Yildiz, M. et al. (2023) 'Solar energy for the airport ground support equipment – a quantitative study', *Aircraft Engineering and Aerospace Technology*, 95(5), pp. 831–837. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEAT-08-2022-0211/FULL/PDF>.
- Zhang, A., Gudmundsson, S.V. and Oum, T.H. (2010) 'Air transport, global warming and the environment', *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 15(1), pp. 1–4. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRD.2009.07.011>.